

From Static Points to Dynamic Fields: Reconstructing Spatiotemporal Boundaries of Places via AutoEncoder and Mobility Big Data

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Abstract

Traditional Geographic Information Systems (GIS) treat places as static points or polygons, ignoring dynamic boundary changes over time. This study introduces an AutoEncoder-based AI framework to reconstruct the spatiotemporal boundaries of places using mobility big data. The model converts human mobility data in neighboring grid cells into a latent space embedding to identify functional homogeneity. Low latent space distances indicate similar synchronized mobility patterns, suggesting they belong to the same functional dynamic field; while high latent space distances signify behavioral divergence, marking the boundaries of a place. Validated with telecom data collected in Taipei, Taiwan, the framework's effectiveness is demonstrated through three case studies: seasonal spatial extent dynamics around National Chengchi University, diurnal spatial extent dynamics around the Wenhua Station of Taipei's rapid transit system, and event-driven spatial extent dynamics around the Taipei Arena. The results validate the efficacy of the proposed framework in delineating dynamic urban rhythms and uncovering fluid functional boundaries that characterize cotemporary urban life.

Keywords: Human Mobility Data, Spatiotemporal Dynamics, AutoEncoder, Latent Space¹

1. Research Objectives

Traditional Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and map services frequently regard place names as static labels associated with individual geographic coordinates, thereby neglecting the dynamic spatial extent associated with the place names. Historically, scholars have relied on static urban zoning maps or physical building footprints for classification. However, these approaches

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often overlook actual human activity patterns. For instance, a downtown area often has very different human mobility patterns throughout a day as well as on weekdays vs. weekends. To bridge this gap and extract latent spatiotemporal semantics, this study introduces an AutoEncoder-based framework with mobility big data. Rather than integrating information into static GIS systems, our primary objective is to model the fluid boundaries of place-based human activities. This approach transforms static “Place Name + Coordinates” representation into dynamic “Place Name + Changing Spatial Extent over Time” insights, more accurately reflecting real-world human behavior.

2. Significance

The primary contribution of this research is to develop an AutoEncoder-based artificial intelligence (AI) framework that can detect and identify dynamic spatial extents of human activities associated with various places based on mobility big data. This framework advances conventional static point representation to a semantic dynamic field representation that captures human activities over time. While conventional time-series similarity metrics (e.g., Pearson correlation, Dynamic Time Warping) and standard clustering algorithms often struggle with high-dimensional noise and are overly sensitive to minor temporal shifts, our approach mitigates these limitations. By leveraging latent space distances rather than traditional clustering, this approach more effectively captures the dynamic activity patterns. This study also offers a dynamic framework for urban decision-making, with direct applications in urban planning, commercial site selection, and large-scale event management.

3. Methodology

The framework is centered around a well-known deep learning model, AutoEncoder [1], as illustrated in *Figure 1*. Upon receiving a place name query, the framework retrieves the corresponding coordinates from existing digital maps and identifies neighboring grids. It then extracts human mobility time series data for these locations, applying a pre-processing algorithm to normalize absolute values and identify mobility dynamics. To capture temporal context, the framework employs a moving time window, aggregating data from the hours preceding and following each timestamp. These moving time windows are treated as temporal snapshots, ensuring that the analysis accounts for short-term behavioral continuity.

This AI-based approach is essential for managing the high-dimensional, noisy, and non-linear characteristics inherent in continuous urban mobility data. The Encoder compresses the data into a low-dimensional latent space, serving as a robust mechanism for non-linear dimensionality reduction that captures the fundamental structures of dynamic human activities. Unlike linear mathematical models, this deep learning process effectively filters out noises and temporal anomalies to extract “characteristic fingerprints” that reflect core behavioral patterns. The Decoder reconstructs the data from this latent space, aiming to minimize Mean Squared Error. The objective of this study is to map the dynamic spatial extent associated with a specific place name. We focus on the local neighborhood of grid cells to delineate the boundaries where a place’s influence ends. By calculating distances in the latent space between a query point and its neighbors, we identify the nearby grid cells that belong to the place name. Distances near zero indicate highly synchronized mobility patterns, serving as a proxy for functional homogeneity in the latent space.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the proposed framework.

In contrast, large distances signify a divergence in spatiotemporal behavior, marking the boundaries where human activity patterns become distinct from the target place. These latent space distances are mapped in the subsequent results section to visualize the gradient of similarity in human mobility dynamics.

4. Results

This study uses validated telecom mobility big data from Taipei City, Taiwan [2], for demonstration. The dataset covers January 1, 2018, to December 31, 2019, segmented into 500×500 meter grids. While the 500-meter resolution is constrained by the available data, it offers a theoretically grounded spatial unit for urban analysis. This resolution aligns with the typical dimensions of urban blocks and the “walking life circle” (approximately 5-10 minutes of walk). Therefore, this resolution level holds substantial utility for community-level mobility analysis and urban planning. The dataset includes coordinates, recording time, and crowd volume, excluding zero crowd volume instances. Three types of places are selected in this study to capture diverse human mobility patterns: (1) places with seasonal or annual spatial extent dynamics, (2) places with diurnal (day-to-night) spatial extent dynamics, and (3) places with spatial extent dynamics influenced by special events. In the following figures, the similarity between locations is quantified by their distance in the latent space. A low latent distance value (darker colors on the map) indicates that the neighboring grid cell shares a highly similar ‘behavioral fingerprint’ with the target location, reflecting their shared spatiotemporal mobility pattern.

Figure 2. Latent Space Distance (representing similarity level) of human mobility trends with respect to Grid #4 where NCCU is located: (a) at 12:00 noon during a semester, (b) at 12:00 noon during a final exam week, (c) at 12:00 noon during a winter break, and (d) at 12:00 noon during a holiday. The color bar indicates the Euclidean distance in the latent space. Lower values (closer to 0.00, shown in darker red) represent higher similarity and greater synchronicity in human mobility patterns, whereas higher values (shown in yellow) indicate increasing behavioral divergence.

4.1. Places with Seasonal or Annual Spatial Extent Dynamics

We select the “National Chengchi University (NCCU)” as an example of places with seasonal or annual spatial extent dynamics since human dynamics around a university is typically influenced by the academic calendar. This example illustrates the changing human mobility patterns around the university main entrance and off-campus residences. In *Figure 2*, Grid #4 covers the university’s main entrance and nearby commercial zones. Grid #7 consists of mainly university’s academic buildings, while Grids #5 and #8 are predominantly residential dormitories. The analyses cover (1) weekdays at 12 PM during a semester, (2) during a final examination week at 12 PM, (3) on weekends, and (4) during a holiday. The results indicate that the latent space distances (denoting similarity) between Grid #7 and Grid #4 vary markedly due to the levels of student presence, whereas Grids #5 and #8 exhibit low latent space distance (denoting high similarity) to Grid #4, forming consistent clusters that reflect residential areas of local residents.

4.2. Places with Diurnal (Day-to-Night) Spatial Extent Dynamics

We choose the Wenhua Station of Taipei Metro's Wenhua Line as a case study of places with diurnal spatial extent dynamics. Situated adjacent to a major technology park, the area is characterized by

Figure 3. Latent Space Distance (representing similarity level) of human mobility trends with respect to Grid #1, where the “Wenhu Station” is located, on work days: (a) commuting peak period (Weekdays, 09:00), (b) commuting off-peak period (Weekdays, 15:00). The colorbar indicates the Euclidean distance in the latent space. Lower values (closer to 0.00, shown in darker red) represent higher similarity and greater synchronicity in human mobility patterns, whereas higher values (shown in yellow) indicate increasing behavioral divergence.

high-volume commuter flows during normal work hours. However, the station exhibits a distinct diurnal shift, transitioning into a primarily residential and commercial hub during non-work hours. Grids #1, #2, and #3 cover the metro line and a main road to the tech park. Grids #1 and #4 are residential; others are parts of a lakeside park. At 9 AM on weekdays, the spatiotemporal dynamics of Grid #1 aligns with Grids #2 and #3, forming a functional cluster indicative of commercial and workplace land use (see *Figure 3a*). By 3 PM, Grid #1 shifts in the latent space to become more like the residential Grid #4 (see *Figure 3b*), demonstrating the latent space’s capability to capture diurnal spatial extent dynamics of a place.

4.3. Places with Spatial Extent Dynamics Influenced by Special Events

“Taipei Arena,” which is a concert and events venue located in a lively commercial district, is used as an example of places with spatial extent dynamics influenced by special events. We examine four distinct scenarios: 3 PM on an event day, 9 PM on an event day, 9 PM on a weekday without an event, and 9 PM on a weekend without an event. The results demonstrate that Taipei Arena’s human mobility patterns diverge significantly from its surroundings only during event evenings, driven by a concentrated influx of attendees (see *Figure 4b*). Conversely, during non-event periods, the venue’s human mobility patterns align closely with the adjacent commercial district, yielding smaller latent space distances (denoting higher similarity) in the latent space and signaling a shared functional rhythm (see *Figure 4a, 4c, 4d*). These results collectively demonstrate the effectiveness of the latent space embeddings, as the extracted features naturally form distinct clusters that mirror underlying land use categories across diverse temporal and contextual conditions.

5. Conclusion

This study introduces a framework that leverages the AutoEncoder AI architecture and human mobility big data to evolve traditional, static point/polygon representation of place into dynamic “field” representations of human mobility associated with different types of places over time. By utilizing the AutoEncoder’s latent space, the framework distills high-dimensional features into

Figure 4. Latent Space Distance (representing similarity level) of human mobility trends with respect to Grid #5, where the “Taipei Arena” is located, on event and non-event days: (a) 15:00 on an event day, (b) 21:00 on an event day, (c) 21:00 on a non-event weekday, and (d) 21:00 on a non-event weekend/holiday. The colorbar indicates the Euclidean distance in the latent space. Lower values (closer to 0.00, shown in darker red) represent higher similarity and greater synchronicity in human mobility patterns, whereas higher values (shown in yellow) indicate increasing behavioral divergence.

patterns that encapsulate temporal signatures and functional intensities of specific locations. The case studies presented in this paper demonstrate the framework's ability to capture evolving human mobility patterns across diverse urban contexts. Crucially, the results uncover latent correlations between urban areas, revealing that spatially distant regions often exhibit synchronized mobility rhythms due to common functions. By transcending the constraints of traditional methods, this AI approach replaces traditional, static point/polygon representation of places with “behavioral fingerprints” of places that reflect underlying spatiotemporal human dynamics. Consequently, it provides a robust approach for adaptive urban planning, strategic commercial site selection, and real-time management of large-scale events.

References

- [1] Hinton GE, Salakhutdinov RR (2006) Reducing the Dimensionality of Data with Neural Networks. *Science* 313(5786):504–507. doi:10.1126/science.1127647
- [2] Chiu SM, Liou YS, Chen YC, Lee C, Shang RK, Chang TY, Zimmermann R (2024) Universal Transfer Framework for Urban Spatio-Temporal Knowledge Based on Radial Basis Function. *IEEE Transactions on Artificial Intelligence* 5(9):4458–4469. doi:10.1109/TAI.2024.3379475